

3rd CYCLONHIT SUMMER SCHOOL

Photoactivable antibacterials: from basic concepts to practical applications

Bologna, September 26 – 28, 2016

VENUE: Bologna, CNR Area della Ricerca
Via Piero Gobetti 101, Centro Congressi, Room 216

ORGANIZERS: Dr. Ilse Manet, ISOF-CNR, ilse.manet@isof.cnr.it
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**UNIVERSITÀ
degli STUDI
di CATANIA**

Monday, September 26

14.15 **OPENING**

14.30-15.30 Formation and deactivation of excited states and excited state properties

Paola Ceroni (Bologna University)

15.30-16.30 Electronic absorption and emission spectroscopy

Barbara Ventura (ISOF-CNR)

16.30-17.00: coffee break

17.00-17.45: Determination of photophysical and photochemical quantum yields.

Serena Silvi (Bologna University)

Tuesday, September 27

9.00-10.00 Electronic absorption and emission spectroscopy with polarized light

Alberto Credi (Bologna University)

10.00-11.00 Time-resolved emission

Giacomo Bergamini (Bologna University)

11.00-11.30: coffee break

11.30 - 12:15 Time-resolved absorption

Mirco Natali (Ferrara University)

12.15 – 13.00 Energy transfer and electron transfer

Andrea Barbieri (ISOF-CNR)

13.00 : lunch

14:30 - 15:15 Laser scanning confocal fluorescence microscopy and super resolution imaging

Ilse Manet (ISOF-CNR)

15.15 – 16.00 Two-photon excitation fluorescence imaging of cells and tissues

Marica Ericson (Gothenburg University)

Wednesday, September 28

9.00 - 10:00 Photosensitizers for photodynamic therapy (PDT) and generation and detection of singlet oxygen

Ilse Manet (ISOF-CNR)

10.00 – 11.00 Polymeric Carrier systems and applications in PDT for bacterial infections

Fabiana Quaglia (Naples University)

11.00-11.30. coffee break

11.30 – 12.30 Nitric oxide photodelivering molecular assemblies for the treatment of infectious diseases

S. Sortino (Catania University)

12.30 : lunch

14.00-15.00 Bactericidal Photoactivable metal-based nanoparticles

S. Sortino (Catania University)

15.00 - 16:00 Photoalkylating Agents and other photoactivable systems with antibacterial potential

Mauro Freccero (Pavia University)

16.00-16.30: coffee break

16.30 – 17.15 Commercialising research: from lab to products

Nanologica's journey as a small company supplying the pharmaceutical industry

Adam Feiler (Nanologica, Sweden)

END OF SCHOOL

We gratefully acknowledge the following companies for their support

